

ONLINE SHOPPING SYSTEM FOR JEWELRY STORE

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Abstract. The Online Shopping System For Jewelry Store is a web-based application designed to streamline the management and sales processes of a jewelry store. The system allows administrators to manage jewelry products, including adding new items, updating existing ones, and removing obsolete products. Each jewelry item has details such as name, description, quantity, price, weight, and an image associated with it. The system also supports categorization of jewelry items for better organization.

Keywords: Jewelry items, administrators, users

INTRODUCTION

The application allows administrators to manage jewelry items, categories, and members. Each piece of jewelry in the system has attributes such as name, description, quantity, price, weight, and an image. The admin can easily add, update, or delete jewelry items and categorize them for better organization. Members can register on the platform, log in to their accounts, and interact with the available jewelry items. When a member logs in, their profile image is displayed in the header, enhancing the personalized experience. Members can view jewelry details, leave comments, and rate the products. These ratings and comments help other users make informed purchasing decisions.

PROBLEM

This system not only streamlines the management of jewelry items but also enhances the user experience by allowing interaction through comments and ratings. Figure 1 and 2 shows the system flow diagram for the user and admin. The system flow diagrams are two of the graphical representations of the flow of data in a system. With the help of the diagram, it is possible to control the event decisions of the system and how data is flowing to the system.

APPROACH

The system is designed with a user-centric approach, ensuring both efficiency and ease of use for administrators and customers alike. The system's backend, developed using the robust Spring Boot framework, ensures scalability and reliability, making it suitable for both small-scale jewelry shops and larger enterprises. Additionally, the integration of a secure MySQL database facilitates efficient data storage and retrieval, allowing for real-time updates

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and seamless user interactions. For administrators, the system offers detailed analytics and reporting features, enabling them to track sales, monitor inventory levels, and understand customer preferences. This data-driven approach empowers store owners to make informed business decisions, ultimately enhancing profitability. On the customer side, the system’s responsive design ensures compatibility across various devices, offering a consistent shopping experience whether accessed via desktop, tablet, or smartphone. Integrated social sharing features further enhance user engagement, allowing customers to share their favorite items with friends and family directly from the platform. As e-commerce continues to grow, this system stands as a critical tool for jewelry businesses, combining functionality, security, and a modern user interface to meet the evolving demands of both the market and consumers.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram for User

Figure 2: System Flow Diagram for Admin

Admins have the authority to manage user accounts, including creating, updating, and deleting users. They are responsible for adding new jewelry items, updating existing inventory, and removing outdated products, ensuring the catalog is always accurate and up-to-date. Additionally, admins can monitor user activity, handle customer queries, and manage payment transactions. They also oversee the system's security by managing access permissions and ensuring that sensitive information is protected. The Admin module plays a critical role in maintaining the overall functionality and security of the jewelry management system.

Figure 3: Database Design

In the Jewelry Store project, the database diagram might depict tables like Member, Order, Cart Item, Order Item, Jewelry, Kpay, JCategory and Sales Report. These tables would be connected through relationships, such as a foreign key linking the Order table to the Member table, indicating which member placed a specific order. Similarly, the Order Item table would be linked to both the Order and Jewelry tables, showing which jewelry items are part of a particular order. The diagram serves as a blueprint for the database, helping developers and stakeholders understand the data flow and dependencies within the system. It also aids in maintaining and expanding the database structure as the project evolves.

RESULTS

After the system is developed, system testing must be carried out to ensure it is free of bugs. If any bugs or errors are detected during testing, the developer must correct and fix them immediately. Testing evaluates the software to detect differences between given input and expected output. It is conducted to assess the system's quality and can be considered a validation and verification process. System testing is not limited to the development team but also involves specific outsiders to test system acceptance. Figure 4 shows the implementation of the Jewelry Shop System.

Figure 4: Implementation of the System

CONCLUSION

The Internet has become a central resource in modern life, making a sophisticated jewelry database system like Taw Win Jewelry Shop indispensable for both administrators and users. This shop offers efficient management of jewelry items data, providing a comprehensive and engaging experience for users who can explore extensive jewelry, add to cart and wish list, and leave review comments. Designed with intuitive navigation and a visually appealing interface, this site ensures quick data retrieval and valuable feedback. The system reduces manual workload, minimizes errors and responsive design. Integrated payment options allow for premium feature upgrades, further enriching the user experience. Overall, Taw Win Store stands out as a leading solution for streamlining items data management and offering a user-centric platform for shopping enthusiasts.

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